

ART STUDIES

НЕКОТОРЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЭТНИЧЕСКОЙ МУЗЫКИ

Арутюнян А.Г.

*Центр арменоведческих исследований Ширака НАН РА,
г. Гюмри Кандидат искусствоведения, доцент*

SOME FEATURES OF ETHNIC MUSIC

Harutyunyan H.

*Shirak Centre for Armenian Studies of NAS RA,
Gyumri PhD in Art, Associate Professor*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Музыка, как наиболее информативный вид духовной культуры, также играет значительную роль в формировании самосознания этноса. Музыка играет важную роль в этнической идентификации. Песня может передавать элементы языка (синтаксические, фонетические, лексические формы), утраченные или нормализованные в других языках. Статья посвящена характеристике типологических особенностей этно-музыки.

ABSTRACT

Music, as one of the most information-intensive types of spiritual culture, also plays a significant role in the formation of the self-awareness of an ethnic group. Music plays a significant role in ethnic identification. A song can convey elements of a language (syntactic, phonetic, lexical forms) that have been lost or normalized in other languages. The article is devoted to the characteristics of the typological features of ethnomusic.

Ключевые слова: этномузыка, этномузыкальное мышление, народное музыкальное творчество, культура; этнос, система, музыкальный стиль, интонация.

Keywords: ethnomusic, ethnomusical thinking, folk music, culture; ethnicity, system, musical style, intonation.

Ethnic culture is a system, the integrity of independent, interconnected of elements. We can name the main components: language, religion, worldview, economy, everyday life, food, law, history, art, etc. Some of presented subsystems (and their system-forming elements) are presented as an invariant that allows preserving the uniqueness of an ethnic group, despite natural, social, political, historical complexity of existence.

It should be noted that ethnic culture is characterized not only by a complex hierarchical organization, internal and external functioning, but also self-regulation, the ability to change one's states, historical (spatio-temporal) dynamics. In this connection, we consider it necessary to turn to synergetics the science of the processes of self-organization of systems of different directions: physical, biological, technical, social, cultural.

Ethnic culture as a nonlinear system due to fluctuations cannot be in a state of equilibrium. The stable steady state inherent in the system itself changes under different conditions. Changes in states are determined both by external influences and the system itself. The elements that make up the system, called oscillators in synergetics, are determined from whole and in interaction with other elements lead themselves differently than they would if they were independent. For studying level of interaction between elements of ethnic culture it is necessary to use structural-functional, multifactorial approaches, typologization methods aimed at identifying a general, functionally related analysis of hierarchically ordered structures.[1, p 3-5]

The artistic activity underlying art is syncretistic, unlike other types of human activities that are dissected and specialized. Artistic activity is formed earlier than other types of activities, since human childhood and the "childhood of humanity" are characterized by a syncretic integrity of consciousness.

Let's focus on one of the art forms - *music*. Music is a temporary, long-lasting form art, in contrast to spatial types of art (sculpture, architecture, painting), the most abstract, allowing in the process of long procedural perception to comprehend dramaturgy images. Music, according to the structure of ethnic culture, also reflects the worldview of the ethnic group, life, traditions, customs.

Musical culture consists of music itself and the spheres of social life that interact with it. It stands out for its greatest ability to unite people around itself, to unite them and carries a huge amount of information about the ethnic group. The manifestation of musical culture of its unifying capabilities is facilitated by its accessibility to the broad masses, the ability to rhythmize human actions and the universality of language.

Musical culture is an integral part of the national culture of any ethnic group. It carries ethnic characteristics along with other types of culture. Musical culture is one of the main components of the process of personal enculturation. Musical culture can serve as one of the means by which one can identify the national traits of a particular people and even identify the ethnic community to which a particular example of musical culture belongs. Music also serves for the self-identification of

an individual both in relation to his own ethnic group and to other ethnic communities.

Rhythm is the basis of musical culture. The sense of rhythm is fundamentally motor in nature. This brief formulation essentially provides a materialistic explanation of the effect of music on the listener. The sense of musical rhythm has not only a motor, but also an emotional nature: it is based on the perception of the expressiveness of music. It is in the rhythmic organization of music that the ethnic uniqueness of musical culture is manifested.

The peculiarities of the rhythmic organization of the musical culture of a particular ethnic group are the element of ethnic culture on the basis of which its identification is made. Musical culture and its rhythmic organization plays a decisive role in the worldview and behavior of an individual, and carries within itself value criteria that allow one to accurately socialize in a given society.

The ethnic uniqueness of musical culture, conditioned by the social history of a particular ethnic group, has great stability - for centuries in one culture or another the same conceptual ideas about the essence of music, its meaning, purpose, and relationship with other branches of art have been retained.

Modern cultural studies are less interested in music than other types of culture, people, religion, technology, science and much more. At the same time, musical culture plays, without exaggeration, a colossal role in the life of modern man. The main purpose of musical culture is in human communication. The peculiarity of musical communication is the unity of people of any size.

Rhythm plays one of the most important roles in the life of all mankind. It is not without reason that many scientists and artists speak about the rhythm of F as the most important element in the life of an individual. The study of the ethnic originality of the rhythmic organization of various cultures is necessary because, in connection with the intensification of the process of globalization that has captured humanity, such a concept as national culture, which includes literature, music and other components of ethnic culture, are gradually disappearing, "dying out", being replaced by a pseudoculture that often does not have no value.

In a musical culture that is formed on level of feeling, the most characteristic national features are persistently preserved. Thematic theme of the musical heritage of ethnic groups is holistic, meaningful and correlates with the category of the universal.

The musical culture of an ethnic group is a system since musical culture represents a holistic

a complex of elements (mentality, intonation, musical thinking, activities for the creation, storage, perception, reproduction of musical values) and all subjects of this type of activity, which are interconnected with each other, it is considered as an element of the system more of a wide order (nature, existence, sphere of social life), while elements of musical culture can be systems of a lower order.

Ethnomusical thinking, which is formed in the process of comprehending folklore material, has its

own specificity in connection with the significant special features that folk musical art has. Folk musical art is an artistic phenomenon, an integrity in which the worldview, worldview and worldview of the people are hidden, and the energy messages of the ancestors are encoded. The folk song combines spiritual meaning, sensual nature, energy and adequate multilingual structure, identity of content achievements and forms, the unity of "subsigns and elementarysigns" [2, p. 11-15]. In folk music, great the amount of information transmitted in the unconscious level by "charging" with special energy during adjusting the human energy field to frequency energy field of folk singing melodies, resonating at its frequency. A folk song is born not as a result of experiencing environmental confrontation of the general world and a person's worldview, how often happens in the classical tradition, but arises out of sympathy position in the world, out of kinship with it, out of love and connection to people and nature. This world-sensing position has a beneficial effect per person, and this is the power of folk musicki, this is its vitality, indestructibility, vitality.

The intonation of the beauty of life – here that permeates the folk melod, and this is the property of the matter - folk music art is attractive for different generations, carries within itself the "space of true worldview" [4, p. 49], with which every chant, phrase, song. In a folk song they merge together "ours" and "alien", and this "alien" is intonation formulas that have been used for centuries, "a sense of mental or" several generations of ancestors in which the combination the wisdom and beauty of their worldview flowed together. In connection with the above, ethnomusical thinking is a process realized in intonation the process of reflecting reality and creative creation giving-correction of subjective images in support on the ideas formed in the musical consciousness national "constants" that carry ethnic originality of worldview and musical language specific people. Ethnomusical thinking is a process of spiritual-intonation communication with the world, people, the community itself combat through ethnomusical language.

Ethnomusical thinking is complex of abilities: ability to holistically intonation reading of information, differentiation of individual signs (meanings, values), the ability to instantly establish understanding the connections between images, intonations (signs, values), the ability to correct semi- the given intonation meanings in accordance with the prescribed rhodopean tradition, the ability to produce introduction of new signs, meanings within the framework of the national style, creative modeling ability given signs (meanings, meanings) in accordance with with your own plans. In musical thinking there are the same types operations, as in ordinary thinking: definition, comparison, analysis, generalization, grouping, classification, judgment, inference. However, during the musical thinking on a folklore basis, a person operates conveys both meanings, knowledge, signs, and intonations, chants, phrases, timbres, constantly adjusting them in accordance with the folk singing tradition of the ethnic group.

Ethnomusical thinking is a process creative. One of the important indicators of developed ethnomusical

thinking is the ability model new musical signs (abstract and specific) based on a wide range of life phenomena and images based on Tradition. Play plays a big role in ethnomusical thinking. There is no musical information as coming from outside, and accumulated in the "memory storeroom", as well as available in the "pantry of the unconscious." In progress obtaining musical information are involved hearing, imagination, musculoskeletal system. Part of the incoming musical information is washed away words, meanings, folded into intonation, is subjected to human musical consciousness assessment and correction tuning in accordance with the inner world of mancentury, another part of the information is accepted unconsciously specifically, at the bodily-motor level; the third part accepted as given, thanks to "pleasantness", "closeness" to the inner world. [3, p 56-57] And the more information, which corresponds to internal potencies soul, the closer the work, the more spiritual experience that belonged to the ethnic group, individuals, the person perceives. The foundations of ethnomusical thinking are laid occur from infancy due to the accumulation a certain stock of intonation-auditory preplacements in the "memory storeroom". Specific part music information already exists thanks to gene memory. In the course of the development of ethnomusical thinking, there is a dialogue with modernity and with the past "episystem", and in dialogue with modern ethnolinguistic culture of a representative of an ethnic group, perceived May new signs, meanings, intonations must be implemented to exert an "ethnic-preserving function", protecting the in national symbols of native music. The ethnic characteristics of folk music are multi-depends on the originality of the singing-melodic system. A theme that has evolved over the centuries in every ethnic group. In many folk melodies there is a combination of typical, expressive, selected by time and national hearing songs that carry national identity to native song melody. These singing intonations, like-tattered and worn from constant use, carry the calls of their ancestors, and each representative of the ethnic with genetic hearing, perceives deeply in the subconscious them and responds to them.

However, every nation has a typical emotional the constant was formatted in a certain way in depending on geographical and historical conditions residence, mentality, national character, theme traditions of the people, and typical national-original chants have become an integral part of the national thinking of each representative of the ethnic group. Some help in ethnomusical thinking nii have body movements, both conscious and unconscious. From this perspective, the intonation becomes bodily-meaning-sound generalization [4. p. 151]. On the native music is generally a phenomenon of "intonation-spiritual-physical, and many musical texts are about one hundred welded with bodily movement, and without bodilyexpressions they lose their attractiveness and inintensity of impact, its energy."

Folk music is "understood by the body", and this happens as a consciously and during conscious action. "Byattention to the body" disturbs the personal and collective new unconscious, and on the basis of impulses

going from them comes the "understanding" of the musical works. At this level a person operates musical intonations as "collapsed highcalls of the whole body" [4, p. 170]. With folklore intonation, hidden intonation unfolds in "gesture-mimic-sound intonation [4, p. 170]. Development of the ability to operate with meanings, knowledge kami within the chant is one of the important greatest abilities. Melos is the main expression body of thoughts and feelings, emotional and semantic coholding. Of great importance for understanding especially musical thinking at this level has interpretation of the modal organization of a folk song. The basis of folk melodies is singing. However the process of the birth of folk melodies, especially late origin, largely depends not only on combining songs, but also from the "struggle" of foundations inside the tune and the "reference points" to which it strives voice. Thus, in the process of formation of the peoplesinging melodies are used. A special role for the formation of a national mulinguistic thinking have "chants-formulas", i.e. tunes that are the result of the originalth process of genre generalization and which performare associated with various verbal texts related to aiming for a certain moment of the ritual or having certain household function. Such tunes are called.They are also standard, polytext.[6]

Musical thinking, formed on folk lore basis, it is impossible without creative operameanings and specific laws, without variation repetition - repetition of any melodic composition plex or chant in a modified form. Variation chant involves combining and rearranging chants, melodic turns, intonations, which, however, in general they do not change their genre affiliation the melody, nor its emotional and semantic essence. When improvising a tune, they play an important role typical songs that serve as strong points mi to create melody. For example, one of the principles variations - "calendar"[3].

Thus, ethnomusical thinking is the ability for analytical-synthetic processing. A combination of abstract and concrete signs, showing specifically in the ability to organize movements folk melodies by moving from foundation to foundation, singing of the foundation, striving for the foundation in the course of alternating of filled and unfilled passages, "closure" let us stand the tune; in the ability to tighten and expand fine-dynamic revolutions, perform jumps and filling jump; in the ability to repeat, alternate, compare, vary the songs; in the ability to organize sound new space in the relationship between musical and rhythmic form and song verse, the ability to operate with breathing in general, honest organization of the melody, the ability to operate formation within the framework of standard structures of syllabic and internal rislog melody, ability to use "formula tunes" in certain context, to comprehend their genre affiliation, ability to operate with themes brahmi depending on the genre of the song, ability to vary signs within a single new genre and stylistic coloring, emotional semantic content, ability to operate with signs in conditions two-voice in the style of heterophony and bourdon diaphony, the ability to connect meanings and acoustics signs with bodily movements that enhance them significance and impact.

Folk music, like music in general, is a phenomenon intonation. Musical folklore is not characteristic Venna character depiction, it carries within itself "the energy of the worldview of a typical representative ethnoses" [4].

The surrounding world is displayed compressed in a generalized, conditional way in sound symbols, and this is not a random phenomenon, and "polished" by centuries of traditionalization. To a greater extent, archaic folk music carries contains a certain emotional tone of our prekovs, "codes" of emotional states, "clumps" of people eternal energy, differently expressed and displayed new. "Intonation-plot prototypes of lo-music localized in the socio-cultural space – time me. The intonation language of music stores memory about its history of mankind" [4, p. 58].

Artistic and figurative language of different nations united in its essential, archetypal forms, that allows people to perceive different nationalities taste music from different ethnic groups and times. Happened generalization of the perception of the world and space by many people and selection of adequate symbols that carried and emotional, and genre, and stylistic, and national peculiar characteristics. [5]

"First Music" world, nature, space is refracted in consciousness and sub the consciousness of the people under the influence of many factors: worldview, national character, social relationships, everyday life. Strong, organized life, growing self-awareness of the people gives rise to strong and developed those tunes. Moreover, in a folk song these typical fabulys are drawn up according to the laws of tradition in a specific national style. As noted by V.V. Medushevsky, "before the size of intonation decreases cultural styles, genres, entire artistic eras along with their contents understanding their social and ideological content. These different streams are compressed into a musical-linguistic intonation of culture – national, historical, in individual-style, figurative-thematic intonations come to life again in the creative phenomena of later times men" [4, p.57].

A folk song is a micromodel of a sounding brass mos, the surrounding world and musical consciousness masses of people of a specific ethnic group, embodied in odefined intonation form and designed in accordance with tradition. It should be noted, however, that a folklore work with developed intonation the onic form is the unity of preintonation (protointonation) and specific intonations reflecting the soul spiritual-sensual meanings. The folk song has simple, complete form, but this form carries itself a holistic model of "sound behavior".

Thus, ethnomusical thinking onthis level includes the ability to communicate with one's ancestors in time, with representatives of the ethnic group in space, ability to operate with emotional-spirits meaningful meanings within the framework of an expanded work with taking into account the subtext (worldviews, life nor the life of the ethnic group), ability to compare new information

with existing experience and the "birth" of a neoplasm personal meaning, "spiritual information" that gives idea of the system "I and the cosmos", "I and the world", "I and other people", ability to operate with specific signs, elements of musical language within the framework of a holistic forms taking into account genre specifics and national originality, the ability to weave and unravelnia".[2, p. 66-67] Of the singing-subvocal tissue, ability to operate with timbres, ability to variation of musical-rhythmiforms in their relationship with song verse, the ability to combine singing with dance movements in compositions and gestures.

CONCLUSION: Ethnomusical thinking involves creatively operating with "subsigns" and signs in accordance with a certain nationally peculiar tradition within the framework of holistic, developed intonation form, operating the formation of artistic "communities" of genre, stylistic, formative order, creation of new meanings, meanings, signs, intonation forms in a certain national folk singing traditionions. It involves creative coordination, correction and modeling of meanings and specific signs at all levels: phonetic, syntactic and compositional within the national tradition. This musical thinking at this stage is represented is a certain instrument through which a person resonates with the "sound of life", a hidden sound pure "harmony of the world", folded into crystals of folklore hay creativity. Possessor of a high level of musical thinking are usually masters singers, people who can not only perform native songs at a high level, but also them, varying the current chants, chants within a certain tradition.

Thus, it can be stated that the ethnolinguistic thinking of an individual is a complex ability, including a figurative reflection of the world, creative correction and creation of images, established connections between them in accordance with folk tradition diction, which allows preserving the folk-singing maintonation skills, ability to compose and vary formation of tunes and echoes, to pass on to future generations of folk musical culture.

References

1. Anzhiganova L.V. Mental foundations of ethnic culture. Abakan, 2000. 93 p. (in Russian)
2. Asafiev B.V. About folk music / Comp. I. Zemtsovsky, A. Kunanbaeva. Leningrad. Musica, 1987. 298 p. (in Russian)
3. Asafiev B. Musical form as a process. Moscow, Musica, 1971. 373 p. (in Russian)
4. Medushevsky V.V. Intonation form of music: Research. Moscow. Composer, 1993. 262 p. (in Russian)
5. Kholopova, V. N. Music as a form of art. Part 1-2. Moscow. 1994 (2nd ed.). 320 p. (in Russian)
6. Semenov V. Social psychology of art. Leningrad, 1998. 118 p. (in Russian)